

THE GENERAL SITUATION ON THE STUDY OF MECHANICAL
BEHAVIORS OF INTERPHASE OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The existence of interphase of composites has been proved. The interphase is composed by the matrix near filler during the process of casting and curing, and it is a concentration place where matrix has a irregular physico-chemico properties and stress gradient and stress singularities occur. It has been shown that the characteristics of the interphase are different from those of fiber or matrix, so it is a independent phase. Many reports show that the properties of the interphase influence all the behaviors of composites, especially the mechanical behaviors. So it is important to study the mechanical characteristics of interphase of composites.

RESEARCH STATE ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS OF INTERPHASE OF
COMPOSITES IN CHINA

1. The Viewpoits Raised in the Study of Mechanical Behaviors of
Interphase of Composites

Experimental results have shown that : the most effect of interphase of composites is on longitudinal and transverse shear strength, and transverse tensile strength. The next is on longitudinal and transverse compressive strength¹. It is just because the calculating model of current strength theory is not reasonable, the difference of strength value between calculating and experiment is great.² It is considered as that one of the improving method is that based on the current strength theory the effect of interphase of composites is added. Only the strength theory considering interphase is hopeful. The

effect of interphase on failure mechanism is very obvious, so interphase can not be neglected in the study of composites.

It is necessary and important to study the effect of interphase of composites on mechanical behaviors of composites and the mechanical behaviors of itself. Especially, making clear the mechanical character of the interphase is important for raising estimative precision and promote the application of composites. However, it is very difficult to study the mechanical behaviors of the interphase, because, at present, the parameters for describing the mechanical properties of interphase can not be measured directly.

For measuring the behaviors of interphase, dynamical method is better than statical method, because the contact level at interphase can not be reflected by means of statical method.

2. The State of Research

The existence of interphase of composites has been proved³. A lot of research about the interphase mainly concentrate on that from the view of chemistry study how the surface treatment of filler affect the mechanical behaviors of composites, or correct the effect of the interphase by means of macro-experiment, a certain lack of the study combining both⁴⁻⁹. There are a few of study on the mechanical behaviors of interphase itself. The results obtained mainly related to particle composite materials. Because the study of fiber-reinforced composites is more difficult than that of particle composites¹⁰.

Most of the results obtained about the mechanical behaviors of interphase are qualitative, for example, the study about the strength theory of matrix and interphase controlling failure in fiber-reinforced composites⁹, about by means of dynamic mechanical inner consume describing the adhesion level at interphase, about the effect of strong or weak adhesion at interphase on expanding way of damage in composites², and so on. But by experiment the thickness and volume fraction of interphase can be calculated^{3,4}, by fiber pullout test etc. part of the strength parameters of interphase can be obtained^{7,11,12}.

At present, in mechanics field, the study of the mechanical behaviors of interphase begin to be paid more attention to.

3. The Way for Experimental Study

(1). In the study of failure process and mechanism of composites, scanning electro-microscope, acoustical emission technique, and soft

X-ray technique are used more and more, but most of the results are qualitative¹³.

(2).By means of fiber pullout test etc. interphase strength and adhesion level can be measured¹².

(3).Use of the dynamic mechanical spectrum of composite materials, for example, DMA, DSC, etc. the thickness and elastic constants of interphase can be estimated^{3,4}.

RESEARCH STATE ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS OF INTERPHASE OF COMPOSITES ABROAD

1. The Viewpoints Raised in the Study of Mechanical Behaviors of Interphase of Composites

It is considered that the interphase of composites is composed by the matrix near filler during the process of casting and curing, and it is a concentration place where matrix has a irregular physico-chemical properties and stress gradient and stress singularities occur. The interphase is independent, inhomogeneous, and anisotropic, and is of itself mechanical, physical and chemical properties¹⁶. All of the research about interphase of composites show that the introduction of interphase in the model of mechanics of composites make some complex phenomenon appeared in composites used in actual engineering get a gut and reasonable explanation¹⁵.

The properties of the interphase mainly depend on the stress field in a thin layer near the filler¹⁶. The interphase is a variable thickness layer, and the layer include all the vary factors¹⁵. So the properties of interphase effect on all of the behaviors of composites. Especially, the interphase control the properties of fiber-reinforced composites. It is considered as a great progress in mechanics of composites that interphase is introduced in the model of mechanics of composites.

In order to get effective composites, the theory on behaviors of interphase and the method for measuring them need to be developed. Establishing the relation between loading way and failure model, fiber strength, and shear strength of interphase, make it possible that whole failure of composites replace the failure of its interphase. However, it is difficult to study directly the physical and chemical structure of interphase, because it is difficult to separate

interphase from composites. So the experiment for studying the interphase is not directly.

2. The State of Research

The research of the mechanical behaviors of interphase of composites is mainly about particle composites, especially, the case of metal flour as filler^{15,17-24}. In short fiber-reinforced composites, according to the model of three-phase and non-ideal adhesion, under external load and temperature difference existence, the tensile stress in fiber, shear stress in interphase, and the stress in matrix have been calculated²⁵. To fiber-reinforced composites, considering the interphase as being homogeneous, isotropic, and complete adhesion, the formulations for calculating the stress in fiber and matrix and shear stress in interphase are given out²⁶.

At the beginning, in the model of three-phase of composites (that is composites is consisted of three phases, i.e., fiber, matrix, and interphase), the interphase is considered as homogeneous, isotropic and the thickness being finite^{23,15,17}. But now it is realized that the interphase is inhomogeneous and anisotropic, and inside the interphase the elastic constants is vary^{27,28}.

To the region of the interphase, there are many models and estimating formulations reported^{24,28,29,17,15,19,21,30}. By means of the elastic constants of interphase, the adhesion level can be described quantitatively (use of adhesive coefficient), but what is the best case of adhesive coefficient, is not still quantitative^{15,31,32}.

From the reports, we can see that the research on elastic constants of interphase is more than on its strength. The problem related to interphase just begin to be paid attention to as it should be.

3. The Way for Experimental Study

To particle composites, the better model of three-phase composites is three-term and N-term model. For fiber-reinforced composites, the current model is two-term and three-term unfolding model¹⁵.

To determine the thickness and elastic constants of interphase, DSC technique or other dynamic measurement technique are used more and more³³.

There are a lot of reports about how to determine the tensile and shear strength of interphase^{14,34-37}. However, up to now, no one method in common use is found.

THE DEVELOPING TENDENCY IN THE STUDY OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS OF INTERPHASE OF COMPOSITES

It is important matter that when calculating the deformation and strength of composites interphase is introduced, and determine and calculate some parameters related to adhesion strength.

To make a thorough study on the problem of properties measurement of inhomogeneous and anisotropic actual composites, expanding the use of classical measurement technique.

It is very important to describe damage level quantitatively and predict nonlinear behaviors of composites.

To study the mechanism of the effect of interphase on strength, life, and toughness of composites.

The knowledge of whole response of composites is not enough to describe completely its surface behaviors, damage occur often at free surface or interface. Developing thermal, mechanical, chemical, and electromagnetical theory and measurement method about surface effect, study the start and expanding of damage in composites.

In one word, the study of mechanical behaviors of interphase of composites just begin. However, it is gratifying that the importance of the effect of interphase on mechanical behaviors of composites has been realized gradually.

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